

Investigation of the Effectiveness of Pumpkin Seed Oil Cake in Treating Synthetic Wastewater Containing Reactive Red 195 Textile Dye

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ABSTRACT

Dyeing agents are organic compounds used in the textile industry to give color to fabrics. These substances include chromophore groups that produce color and functional groups that allow bonding to fibers. Reactive dyes form covalent bonds with the hydroxyl groups of fibers, resulting in permanent coloring, which is why they are widely preferred in the industry. Reactive Red 195 (RR195), one of the most common dyes, is a water-soluble bifunctional azo dye containing vinylsulphone and monochlorothiazine. It is non-degradable in aerobic environments and turns into carcinogenic aromatic amines in anaerobic conditions. This project aims to remove RR195 dyes from wastewater using adsorption methods, which are inexpensive and effective. Pumpkin seed oil cake (PSOC) will be used as the adsorbent. This waste material is leftover after cold-pressing oil and offers an environmentally friendly alternative. The optimal conditions identified are 0.9 g, 10 mg/L, 50 °C, 150 rpm, pH 4 and 15 minutes. Based on the data obtained under these conditions, a 93% removal rate was achieved, indicating successful treatment of Reactive Red 195.

Keywords: Wastewater, Reactive Red 195, Pumpkin seed oil cake, Adsorption

1. INTRODUCTION

Our planet faces an unprecedented level of pollution, mainly caused by growing industrialization and urban expansion. Therefore, creating innovative methods to access clean water sources and support sustainable development has become critical. The leading source of environmental pollution is the release of industrial waste containing hazardous substances such as dissolved metals, phenols, dyes, drug residues, and polycyclic compounds into waterways without proper treatment. The presence of various pollutants causes serious hygiene and sanitation issues in the world's poorest regions and severely worsens water quality in most industrialized countries. The textile industry also significantly harms the environment through the discharge of toxic waste. Dyes, especially reactive dyes, are a major part of this damage. To meet global demand, roughly 0.7 to 1.6 million tonnes of synthetic dyes are produced annually, with about 10-15% being discharged into wastewater. These colored waste materials threaten aquatic ecosystems because of their toxicity, persistence, and resistance to biological breakdown [1]. These dyes, found in wastewater, can cause cancer and tumors when they exceed

Globally, reactive dyes make up 12% of all dye use. They are favored for their high effectiveness in dyeing fibers like wool, cotton, and cellulose. Their molecular structures include $-N=N-$ (azo) and $-SO_3H$ (sulfonate) groups, which make them especially good for wastewater treatment. One of the most popular reactive dyes is reactive red 195 [2,3].

Many different methods can be used to treat wastewater. These include filtration, reverse osmosis, coagulation-flocculation, and adsorption [4]. For this purpose, pumpkin (*Cucurbita pepo* L.) seed oil meal, a natural material, is used as an adsorbent. This natural adsorbent, which has a significant production worldwide, is a vegetable species belonging to the Cucurbitaceae family [5]. Pumpkin seed oil (PSO), besides its high nutritional value and biological effects, has

demonstrated effective results in treating intestinal parasites and hair loss [6-8]. During the oil extraction process, pumpkin seed oil cake (PSOC) is generated as a secondary by-product and is typically used for animal feed or discarded [9,10].

In this study, the removal of reactive red 195 dyes used in the textile industry from aqueous solution was achieved using the adsorption technique with pumpkin seed oil cake. The effects of various operating parameters (adsorbent amount, initial dye concentration, temperature, mixing speed, pH, and time) on the adsorption process were examined in terms of % removal values.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Materials and Reagents

The pumpkin seed oil cake used as the adsorbent material was obtained from an oil factory in İstanbul. After extracting oil from pumpkin seeds using the cold press method, the remaining pulp was granulated. It was then passed through a 24-mesh sieve and made ready for use. The Reactive Red 195 (RR195) dyes were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Dye solutions were prepared as 100 mg/L stock solutions. Appropriate working solutions were prepared from the stock dye solutions using water from the Mikrotest MSD-08 purification system. Mixing was performed using a Julabo SW22 shaking water bath. An Agilent 8453 spectrophotometer was used for UV-VIS measurements.

2.2 The Adsorption Procedure of RR195

The experimental methodology employed in this study comprised batch experimentation. A working solution with an initial dye concentration of 30 mg/L was prepared by mixing appropriate amounts of 100 mg/L Reactive Red 195 stock solutions. 50 mL of the dye solution at a concentration of 30 mg/L was taken into a 100 mL beaker.

A specific weight of adsorbent material was added to it, and the mixture was stirred for particular periods on a shaking water bath. The absorbance values of the samples taken were

measured using a UV spectrophotometer. The reactive red 195 dye was measured at a maximum wavelength of 532 nm. The solution concentrations were calculated using the specified standard measurement curve. In addition, the % removal values of the RR195 dyes were calculated according to Equation 1 stated below.

$$\% \text{Removal} = [(C_0 - C) / C_0] \times 100 \quad (1)$$

C_0 (mg/L) denotes the initial concentration of the dyestuff, while C (mg/L) indicates the amount of dyestuff in the solution at any given time.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Effect of adsorbent amount on RR195 % removal value

In order to study the effect of the adsorbent, 50 mL of a 30 mg/L RR195 solution was taken into a 100 mL beaker. 0.1-1.5 g of adsorbent was added to the solution in the beaker. The beaker was placed on a shaker and shaken at 25 °C, 150 rpm for 30 minutes. It was then filtered through filter paper. The sample obtained was measured at 532 nm in a spectrophotometer, and the solution concentration was determined. The % removal values were determined using Equation 1, and the resulting values are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Effect of adsorbent amount on the RR195 adsorption process.

As shown in Figure 1, the % removal values range from 20% to 86%. The highest removal was 86% using 0.9 g of adsorbent. The decrease in % removal observed beyond this point is likely due to dye molecules not fully reaching the attachment sites on the adsorbent surface because of the increased amount of adsorbent, and the higher adsorbent density causing a repulsive force.

3.2 Initial RR195 concentration

In order to investigate the effect of the initial concentration of RR195 dye on adsorption, RR195 initial concentrations ranging from 10 mg/L to 50 mg/L were prepared for the studies. A 50 mL portion was placed into 100 mL beakers. 0.9 g of adsorbent was weighed and added to them. They were shaken at 25 °C, 150 rpm for 30 minutes. The samples were measured by using a spectrophotometer, and the solution concentration was determined.

Figure 2. Effect of the initial concentration on RR195 adsorption process

Examining the data in Figure 2 shows that the highest removal percentage, 88.3%, was achieved at a dye concentration of 10 mg/L. The decrease in removal percentage at higher concentrations can be explained by the fact that the adsorbent's attachment surfaces are fully occupied, so as the number of dye molecules increases, there are fewer available surfaces for attachment.

3.3 Investigation of the temperature effect on RR195 adsorption

To investigate the effect of temperature on RR195 adsorption, the ambient temperature was varied between 20–50°C in the experiments. 50 mL of a 10 mg/L solution was placed into 100 mL beakers. 0.9 g of adsorbent was weighed and added to each. They were shaken at 150 rpm for 30 minutes. The samples were measured at 532 nm using a spectrophotometer after the adsorption procedure.

Figure 3. Effect of the ambient temperature on RR195 adsorption.

As shown in Figure 3, the highest removal percentage was achieved at a temperature of 50°C. This value, which is 86.0%, indicates that dye molecules can access more areas on the adsorbent surface with increased kinetic energy at higher temperatures, leading to greater removal.

3.4 Agitation speed

To investigate the effect of shaking speed, 50 mL of a 10 mg/L RR195 solution was transferred to a 100 mL beaker. The optimum amount of adsorbent, 0.9 g, was weighed and added to the solution in the beaker. The beaker contents were stirred at speeds ranging from 120 to 180 rpm at 50°C for 30 minutes. The % removal values were calculated according to Formula 1, and the values found are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Effect of the agitation speed on RR195 adsorption process

As shown in Figure 4, the adsorption process at 150 rpm achieved a removal efficiency of 90.9%. It is believed that at lower agitation speeds, the number of dye molecules reaching the adsorbent surface did not reach its maximum. At higher speeds, adsorption efficiency decreased due to negative effects on the bonds formed between the dye and the adsorbent.

3.5 pH Effect

In order to examine the effect of pH on RR195 adsorption, 50 mL of a 10 mg/L RR195 solution was taken into a 100 mL beaker. The optimum weighing amount of 0.9 g of adsorbent was weighed and added to the solution in the beaker. The beaker contents were adjusted to pH values of 4, 7, and 10. Then, it was shaken at 150 rpm for 30 minutes at 50 °C. Subsequently, it was filtered through filter paper. The % removal values are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Effect of the pH on the RR195 adsorption process

When the data in Figure 5 is examined, it is seen that the highest removal value of 92.5% was achieved at pH 4. It is understood that the increasing amount of OH^- at higher pH values increases the ionic charge, and this density negatively affects the adsorption process.

3.6 Time effect on RR195 adsorption

To examine the impact of shaking duration on RR195 adsorption, a 50 mL sample of a 10 mg/L RR195 solution was placed in a 100 mL beaker. An optimal amount of 0.9 g of adsorbent was weighed and added to the solution in the beaker. The beaker contents were stirred at 50°C, 150 rpm, and pH 4 for 5 to 180 minutes. The % removal values are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Effect of the agitation time on the RR195 adsorption process

According to Figure 6, an adsorption time of 15 minutes, which results in a 93.0% removal efficiency, was identified as optimal. Shorter durations suggest that sufficient interaction between dye molecules and the adsorbent surface has not yet been achieved, so the % removal value has not yet reached its maximum. Beyond 15 minutes, a decline in the % removal value is observed. It is believed that longer adsorption times cause dye molecules attached to the adsorbent to desorb, thereby decreasing the removal efficiency.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

In experimental studies to remove RR195 dye, a commonly used coloring agent in the textile industry, from water solutions, pumpkin seed oil cake was employed as an adsorbent. The results showed that the optimal conditions for RR195 removal are 0.9 grams of pumpkin seed oil cake, a RR195 concentration of 10 mg/L, an ambient temperature of 50 °C, a shaking speed of 150 rpm, pH 4, and a 15-minute operating time. Under these conditions, a removal efficiency of 93.0% was achieved. Pumpkin seed oil cake, a natural material often used as animal feed or discarded as waste, appears to be an effective adsorbent for removing RR195 textile dye from water. This natural adsorbent is expected to help conserve water resources.

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